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Editors
Remus Ion Iacobescu
Annelies Malfliet

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BAUXITE RESIDUE SINTER PHASE TRANSFORMATIONS

Harrison HODGE^{1*}, Pritii TAM², James VAUGHAN¹, Dimitris PANIAS²

¹ School of Chemical Engineering, University of Queensland, Australia

² National Technical University of Athens

*h.hodge@uq.edu.au**, *priti.tam@metal.ntua.gr*, *james.vaughan@uq.edu.au*,
panias@metal.ntua.gr

Introduction

Bauxite residue (BR) contains between 2 and 35 wt% aluminium (expressed as Al₂O₃)¹. This aluminium is lost from Bayer process, primarily due to the formation of sodium containing desilication products (DSP), incomplete digestion of aluminium bearing minerals and in some cases early precipitation of gibbsite. The sintering process has been used commercially in the processing of high silica bauxites and could be used effectively for the recovery of aluminium and sodium values from bauxite residue (BR). In the sinter process BR is calcined with Na₂CO₃ to produce a soluble NaAlO₂ product, while stabilising the silicates with CaO². The recovery of this material is the first step in total BR valorisation. In this research, two distinct BRs are characterised before and after sintering. The mineralogy was quantified using XDB^{4,5}. Key reaction equilibrium was considered using the Factsage thermodynamic modelling package⁵, contributing to the understanding of potential reaction pathways during sintering.

Experimental

Sintering was conducted at 900°C for 2 hours, in an air atmosphere. Between 20-30 minutes was taken to reach reaction temperature before being held for the reaction time and cooled in the furnace overnight. Two tests were completed per residue, one with CaO ((S + Ca AU/GR), 1 g BR: 0.25 g Na₂CO₃: 0.2 g CaO) and one without CaO ((S AU/GR), 1 g BR: 0.25 g Na₂CO₃). This amounts to molar ratios of 4.6 and 1.4 for the Greek BR and 1.4 and 2 for the Australian BR's for Ca:Si and Na:Al respectively. Factsage software was used to estimate equilibrium data for both observed and predicted reactions based on the outputs of the quantitative mineralogy as estimated by XDB software. XDB software uses a full-profile fit method where the measured spectra are fit to a composite of mineral standards in the database. To find an optimum peak fit and respect the mass balance, scale factors are applied. While this approach has limitations as the XDB database does not have a complete set of sinter product references, it provides a good indication of relative abundances of phases.

Results

Table 1 presents the BRs and sintered product composition (measured by XRF). Australian (AU) BR is high in sodium and silicon while Greek (GR) BR is high in calcium.

Table 1: Sample compositions (dry weight basis wt%, ¹Estimated LOI%)

Sample	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	LOI
BR AU	18.5	1.7	42.0	9.0	15.3	6.4	6.2
BR GR	19.3	9.6	43.5	2.8	6.5	5.5	9.4
S AU	16.0	1.6	36.4	20.6	13.3	5.5	2.1
S GR	18.7	9.1	41.0	16.5	5.8	5.0	2.5 ¹
S + Ca Au	14.3	14.8	32.2	18.3	12.1	4.9	2.5
S + Ca GR	16.3	19.7	36.0	14.5	5.1	4.4	2.5 ¹

Figure 1 shows that the major differences between residues stem primarily from the aluminium-containing compounds, which is diaspore (α -AlOOH, **1**) and DSP (cancrinite ($\text{Na}_8(\text{Al,Si})_{12}\text{O}_{24}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, **2**)) for GR BR. AU BR has mostly DSP (sodalite ($\text{Na}_4(\text{Al,Si})_6\text{O}_{12}(\text{OH})1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, **3**)) with minor boehmite (γ -AlOOH, **4**) and gibbsite ($\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, **5**). Titanium in GR BR exists primarily as perovskite (CaTiO_3 , **6**) compared to rutile and anatase (TiO_2 , **7**) in AU BR. GR BR also contains grossular phases ($\text{Ca}_3\text{FeAl}(\text{SiO}_4)((\text{OH})_4)_2$, **8**) which have no analogue in the AU sample.

Aluminium phases reacted to produce sodium aluminate (NaAlO_2 , **9**) or sodium aluminium silicate (NaAlSiO_4 , **10**), with up to 70% of aluminium value recovered. In some cases (S Au and S GR), some residual DSP phases remained. Substantial hematite (Fe_2O_3 , **11**) remained in all cases. In systems with no added CaO (with exception of existing calcite, CaCO_3 , **12**), the formation of sodium ferrite (NaFeO_2 , **13**) and ferrotitanate (NaFeTiO_4 , **14**) was seen. Addition of CaO (**15**) reduced the presence of these compounds in favour of harmunite (CaFeO_4 , **16**), Brownmillerite ($\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$, **17**) and CaTiO_3 . Calcium silicates were also formed (Ca_2SiO_4 , Ca_3SiO_5 , **18**). The unaccounted sodium and silicon was assumed to exist as amorphous Na_2O or SiO_2 . A number of complex phases, notably garnet ($3(\text{Ca,Fe,Mg})\text{O}(\text{Al,Fe})_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{SiO}_2$, **19**), were also detected.

Figure 1: XRD patterns for both residues and all sinter products

Figure 2: Estimated mineral phases from XDB for Australian BR and sinters

Figure 3: Estimated mineral phases from XDB for Greek BR and sinters

Outputs from XDB (AU and GR samples, Figure 2 and 3) indicate that Al(OH)₃ and AlOOH reacted directly with Na₂CO₃ (Equations (1) and (2)).

DSP reacts with CaO to produce Ca₂SiO₄ and NaAlO₂ (Equation (3)). This is expected to be the primary DSP reaction in GR residue. However, because of AU BR's naturally low CaO content, different reactions occur when only Na₂CO₃ is added, indicating an indirect reaction pathways. DSP phases are approximated as nepheline (NaAlSiO₄, Equation (3)) in Factsage due to database limitations as it mirrored major constituent elements of DSP in approximately the same ratios (Na:Al:Si = 1:1:1).

CaO addition did not result in the formation of any additional NaAlO₂ in AU BR whereas there is reduction of NaAlO₂ formed in GR BR. The increased Ca: Si mole ratio, for the GR sinter mix, resulted in unwanted side reactions causing lower NaAlO₂. The formation of CaFe₂O₄ occurs via a two-stage process with Ca₂Fe₂O₅ formed first, while CaO is in abundance, followed by CaFe₂O₄.

Figure 4 depicts the sintering reactions observed in the sintering process. It should be noted that some minerals in the third row will also form when only Na_2CO_3 is added in GR sinters due to its high existing calcium content. Dotted lines indicate compounds which were detected but specific reactions could not be identified.

Figure 4: Map of potential reactions. Equilibrium constant presented as $\log K_{eq}$

In summary, the incorporation of both thermodynamic study and quantitative mineralogical analysis can be useful to understand sinter mineral phase formations, though further works in optimising the sintering system should include changes to operating temperature and reagents dosages.

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